

Fact Sheet: The Dance of Life¹

In this fact sheet, we present a series of paintings which make up a framework called the Dance of Life. This framework was developed by Professor Helen Milroy.

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The Dance of Life depicts a multi-dimensional model of health and wellbeing, from the perspective of First Nations peoples. It brings together the **physical, psychological, social, spiritual, and cultural** dimensions of healing and restoring wellbeing. The stories of our ancestors, the collective grief, as well as healing, begin from knowing where we have come from and where we are heading. From the Aboriginal perspective, carrying the past with you into the future is, as it should be. We are nothing if not for those who have been before us and the children of the future will look back and reflect on us today. When we enable a person to restore all the dimensions of their life, then we have achieved a great deal. When all the dimensions are in balance, within the universe, we can break free of our shackles and truly dance through life.

Within each dimension, there are many layers to be considered, these are:

¹ The Dance of Life, Milroy, H. (2006). <https://www.ranzcp.org/practice-education/aboriginal-torres-strait-islander-mental-health/the-dance-of-life>

The Physical Dimension

Born from Country

We are born from country and at the end of our days we return to country. This human tree has the sky for a roof, the air for walls and the earth as its floor. It freely reaches up to the sky and is warmed by the sun, cooled by the breeze, and exists in perfect harmony with the environment. The body is grounded in the earth rather than being controlled by the mind. At the end of its days, it returns to the earth to be incorporated into the next landscape, providing a continuity of existence forever.

The Psychological Dimension

Living life

Throughout life we make rich two-way connections from every direction possible. We experience our environment through all our senses simultaneously, and the central core of psychological life is alive and constantly growing. This inner core is supported and protected by layers of experience, knowledge, and wisdom, but we can still be aware of our external environment and make our own decisions. Struggles within are comforted by a collective consciousness, a cushion on which to rest.

The Social Dimension

Community Strong Together

First, we acknowledge the central core of the family tree, with its many rings representing the presence of past generations. The family stand on the outer ring, linked together with their children and providing for them a place on which to stand. The shapes formed in between the figures represent the hearts shared in the community and the notion that to lose one child will destroy more than one heart. When a community stands strong together it blossoms, protects us from adversity, and is a part of our strength and wellbeing going forward.

The Spiritual Dimension

The Tree of Life

The tree of life connects the inner core of the earth to the outer dimensions of the universe. It not only connects us but also protects us from all things outside our earthly existence. Life, death, life in this realm is about the richness and intricacies of all of creation of which we form only a very small but essential part in this never-ending cycle. This timeless dimension with its infinite capacity exists within yet outside of our physical realm and keeps us connected for eternity.

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The Cultural Dimension

Healing, Ceremony and Law/Lore

This painting takes the form of three figures symbolising healing, ceremony, and traditional law/lore. All three are intimately connected and weave a pattern throughout life extending into the outer heavens. The life force flows between the figures to represent the vibrancy and dynamic nature of culture. The campfire symbolises the community orientation as well as the cleansing properties of smoke carrying the burdens of life into the universe. Culture is grounded in the land we belong to as much of the law/lore, ceremony and healing comes from country.

As you can see, there are several dimensions, each with several layers that require consideration when developing a comprehensive approach to understanding the mental health of First Nations peoples as well as providing assessment and treatment. The following framework lists several factors operating at the individual, family, community, or broader societal level that could be impacting on mental health and wellbeing. Although many factors lie outside the responsibility of the mental health sector, mental health professionals play a vital role in advocacy and in working collaboratively across sectors to improve outcomes for First Nations families.

Mental health professionals have a sphere of influence and respect in broader society that can facilitate the process of reconciliation and social justice. Risk and protective factors as well as the concept of resilience needs to be understood through a First Nations peoples' lens. This allows for the appropriate development of mental health promotion, prevention, and early intervention programmes. Given the magnitude of the historical legacy combined with contemporary complexities, it is essential to be able to understand what influences behaviour, symptom formation and response to treatment.

Clinicians need to be able to tease out the impact of disadvantage and discrimination, be able to recognise illness in the midst of cultural and spiritual complexity and ambiguity, and attempt to address the many factors impacting on wellbeing. Incorporating historical and cultural perspectives as well as flexibility in approach will enhance the clinician's skills and knowledge and provide a platform for meaningful and respectful cross-cultural exchange.

DIMENSIONS	TRADITIONAL	HISTORICAL	CONTEMPORARY	GAPS IN KNOWLEDGE	SOLUTIONS
PHYSICAL 	Earth as 'Mother' & Nature as family Connection to country as a source of renewal Traditional medicine Traditional diet and activity Good health and wellbeing	Physical genocide Dispossession (being 'uprooted') Environmental degradation Rapid change in diet Incarceration Institutionalisation Forced labour Ill-health, exposure to disease	Population changes Present morbidity and burden of chronic illness Burden of care on children Land-rights and treaty Holistic view Urban, rural, and remote differences Exclusion from health	Stress, immunity, and chronic disease Grief and mortality Transgenerational trauma and physical health Chronic illness and mental health Complimentary healing practices	Sovereignty and Native Title Equity and access Accountability Traditional diet, medicines, and healers Connection to country Holistic medicine Best Start to Life Basic requirements
PSYCHOLOGICAL 	Different concepts, beliefs and meaning Sense of self External attributions; Site of distress Shared learning, cognitive development Identity and role Autonomy and relatedness Life continuum, belonging Birth & bereavement	Psychological Genocide Profound trauma and abuse Loss and grief Extreme powerlessness Misdiagnosis, mislabelling, and re-traumatisation	Place in society Present trauma, loss, grief Future uncertainty Psychological morbidity, illness Identity issues Psychological strengths Apology International perspective Exclusion from humanity	Appropriate Diagnostic Systems and treatment options Culturally valid tools Appropriate Outcomes Accountability measures Impact of racism and discrimination Cultural and spiritual phenomenology Culture bound syndromes	Truth in history National 'Sorry Day' Human rights Safe development, future assurance Inclusiveness Pride, positive images Professional development Indigenous therapies for grief and trauma Addressing 'stress' Identifying and tackling racism
SOCIAL 	Community centred Kinship system Attachment and Child rearing Early autonomy Country as home and kin Collective Vs Individual Obligation and reciprocity Two-way sharing	Social genocide Stolen Generations Racism and apartheid Slave labour	Changing role of family, especially men Role models Family disruption and isolation Loss of buffering Removal of children and adults Paternity Present disadvantage Exclusion from society Reconciliation	Family therapies Children's needs Vs Family Community outcomes Systemic barriers	Social Justice Social determinants Generational view (long term commitment) Whole of life concept Tracing family Restoring Kinship Recording Oral histories Narrative therapies Empowerment Representative body
SPIRITUAL 	Origins of life Dreaming Belonging and connectivity Philosophical views Beliefs Experiences Healing	Spiritual genocide Impact of mission life Imposition of Christianity	Value of wisdom Intolerance Understanding difference Exclusion from existence	Spirituality and Health Existential Despair	Central to health of Australia Healing Understanding with tolerance and respect Purpose and future hope
CULTURAL 	Lore/Law Language Ceremony Healing Beliefs Expression Experiences	Cultural genocide Misinterpretation Tokenism Sacrilege	Cultural clash between two worlds Cultural mix Cultural practices (appropriate for age and gender) Endurance and resilience Cultural knowledge	Continuum of cultural identity Diversity of practice and experience Models of care	Acceptance National Identity Compensation Cultural Renaissance Self-determination Indigenous Governance Cultural security